

FABRICATION AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF POLYCAPROLACTONE/STARCH BLENDS WITH CORN BASED COUPLING AGENT

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1 Introduction

Polycaprolactone (PCL) is being developed as the material of scaffolds for tissue engineering [1]. PCL is considered having fair mechanical properties and characteristics of potentials for load bearing applications, including cardiovascular, dental, and musculoskeletal [1-4]. Yet, its implementation faces some issues, e.g. inadequate mechanical properties, bioresorbability, and hydrophilicity [1,5]. Possible way in an attempt to address these issues is by compounding with other biocompatible materials, and starch is of interest.

Immiscibility is an issue in blending starch to PCL. It leads to deteriorating mechanical properties and may affect the blend's overall performance. Considering the intended applications, options are limited in compatibilizing these constituents where any substance to be incorporated into the blend should also be biocompatible. Previous studies for compatibilizing PCL and starch reported the use of predried starch [6], chlorinated starch (by using methanesulfonylchloride in dimethylformamide) [7], glycidyl methacrylate [8], and plasticizer [9]. The use of those compatibilizing agents resulted some improvements on physical properties of the PCL/starch blends but did not solve the immiscibility problem.

In the purpose of similar attempt to address the issue, this study proposes the use of zein, a prolamine protein from corn. Zein is amphiphilic, having affinity for both polar and non-polar groups [10]. Zein was used as coupling agent for natural fiber/thermoplastic composite and resulted in enhanced mechanical properties [11], an indication of improved miscibility between its constituents.

This potential of zein as coupling agent is expected to be exhibited for PCL/starch blends in the forms of improved physical properties and compatibility with bone cells during short term in vitro evaluation.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

The polycaprolactone has average molecular weight, M_n , of 80,000 and density of 1.145 g/mL at 25°C, as informed by the supplier (Aldrich). The starch used was edible corn starch consisting of 95% corn starch and 5% wheat flour. Zein was supplied in the form of yellowish powder by Sigma. Specimens were prepared by melt-mixing at 120±20°C using Mini Max Molder (Custom Scientific Instruments) and subsequent injection molding to dies of ASTM D638 type V. Blends' composition is denoted in Table 1.

Table 1. Composition of the blends.

Code name	PCL	starch	zein
PCL	100	0	0
PCL/S10	90	10	0
PCL/S10/Z	88	10	2
PCL/S20	80	20	0
PCL/S20/Z	78	20	2

2.2 Characterization and Testing

Tensile specimens were prepared by melt mixing at 120±20°C and subsequent injection molding to dies of ASTM D638 type V, using Mini Max Molder

(Custom Scientific Instruments). Houndsfield H5KT (Tinius Olsen) with 5 kN load cell was used for the tensile tests. The cross head speed for tensile testing neat PCL and its blends was 5 mm/min.

In determining the significance of starch content and zein addition to mechanical properties, statistical analysis was used. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used, set at probabilistic value, $Prob > F$, of maximum 5% as the criterion for the variables to be considered significant.

Thermal analysis was conducted using Perkin-Elmer DSC 7 differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) set for scanning from 20 to 80°C at 10°C/min under nitrogen atmosphere. The observed output was melting temperature (T_m), heat of fusion (ΔH_f), and crystallinity. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was conducted on selected samples using Thermo Scientific Nicolet iS10 with KBr/Ge beam splitter. The FTIR spectra were recorded from 4000 to 600 cm^{-1} with 2 cm^{-1} resolution, averaged over 32 scans. For morphology analysis, scanning electron microscope (SEM) JEOL JSM 5800 was used.

To evaluate hydrophilicity, contact angle measurement was conducted using pendant drop tensiometer Krüss DSA100. Contact angle was measured from the interface between the specimen and the droplet of 2 μl distilled water on specimen's surface. Further evaluation was conducted by analyzing the blends' tendency to absorb simulated body fluid. PCL and its blends were immersed for 24 hours in saline solution at 37°C and their weight gain was measured.

2.3 In vitro analysis

For in vitro analysis of the blends, human bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells were seeded and cultured on selected samples. The isolation, seeding, incubation, and cultivation procedures were according to previous experiences reported elsewhere [12,13].

Mononuclear cells were plated into tissue culture flasks in expansion medium, consisted of Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM, Invitrogen) and 10% fetal bovine serum (Cambrex), at a density of 5×10^4 cells/ cm^2 . Upon reaching 80% confluency, cells were detached with Accutase (Innovative Cell Technologies) and replated at a density of approximately 1×10^4 cells/ cm^2 . The cells were then expanded further for two to six passages.

For assessment of cell proliferation, an MTT assay (Sigma) was used. Cell-cultured specimens after 1 and 14 days of incubation were transferred to a 6 well plate, and serum-free DMEM supplemented with MTT (0.33 mg/ml) was added to each well. The plates were then incubated in the dark at 37°C in an atmosphere containing 5% CO_2 for 2 hours, aspirating the supernatant. Isopropyl alcohol (1 ml) containing 0.04 N HCl was added and the plate was shaken slowly for 15 min. The absorption was measured at 540 nm.

3 Results and Discussion

From tensile test (overall results shown in Table 2), the blend's strength reduced and its stiffness increased with higher starch content, a common indication of immiscibility. Addition of zein does not improve the blend's mechanical properties, except for increased stiffness for blend with 10% starch.

ANOVA for tensile strength and modulus unveiled that only starch content was considered significant in affecting the mechanical properties of the blend. Addition of zein was not significant enough to influence the blend's strength and stiffness.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of the blends.

Type	Yield strength	E	Elongation
	(MPa)	(MPa)	(%)
PCL	16.37 ± 1.67	159.38 ± 11.35	18.46 ± 1.31
PCL/S10	16.03 ± 1.66	159.14 ± 10.88	16.80 ± 1.43
PCL/S10/Z	15.22 ± 1.25	163.18 ± 9.02	16.30 ± 0.80
PCL/S20	14.36 ± 0.32	174.07 ± 6.82	12.60 ± 2.26
PCL/S20/Z	13.35 ± 1.04	169.79 ± 9.37	13.81 ± 0.91

Zein, like starch, is a relatively high modulus thermoplastic [14]. Therefore, addition of zein increases the blend's stiffness, including when compared to that of neat PCL. Yet, yield strength of the blend decreases with addition of zein. Considering that PCL is a good dispersant of fillers, it indicates that zein also has high mobility, causing instability within the PCL matrix when tensile loaded.

FTIR analysis on PCL, starch, zein, and the blends indicated that the spectra of both PCL/starch and PCL/starch/zein blends are similar to that of neat PCL. Peak around 1700 cm^{-1} for internal ester group of the PCL within blends was not affected by

internal C—O—C (around 1650 cm⁻¹) of the starch or bands of amide II (1750–1600 cm⁻¹) of the zein [7,15]. This implies that no molecular bond occurred between PCL and starch or zein.

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of PCL and its blends.

Thermal analysis Table 3 disclosed slight change in melting point of the blends compared to that of neat PCL. In term of crystallinity, addition of starch causes the blend to be less crystalline while adding zein on the blend increases its crystallinity. Higher crystallinity often relates to increased mechanical properties. In this case, although zein increases crystallinity of the PCL matrix, it does not translate to higher strength of the blend. This means interfaces between PCL and zein do not adhere well.

Table 3. DSC analysis on the blends.

Type	T_m	ΔH_f ^{a)}	Crystallinity ^{b)}
	(^o C)	J/g	%
PCL	62.14	62.59	44.9
PCL/S10	62.94	55.30	44.0
PCL/S10/Z	60.94	56.87	46.3
PCL/S20	60.17	50.48	45.2
PCL/S20/Z	61.31	59.33	54.5

^{a)} Per gram of total sample

^{b)} Based on unit mass of PCL component

Image analysis on the blend using SEM (Fig. 2) confirmed the immiscibility of starch on PCL. Zein surface partially adhered to PCL. Yet, starch and zein particles were not compounded.

Contact angle of the blend decreased with more fillers (both starch and zein) content (Table 5). The blend became more hydrophilic with addition of zein, likely due to the hydrophilic portion of its molecules. Immersion of the blends in saline solution showed higher weight gain occurred on the blends compared

to neat PCL (Fig. 3). This indicates better wettability when starch and zein is added to PCL. Similar to the results shown on the blend's surface (by contact angle measurement), simulated body fluid also penetrated the blend better with addition of zein.

Fig. 2. Image of (a) PCL/S10 and (b) PCL/S10/Z.

Table 5. Contact angle measurement.

Type	Contact angle (deg)
PCL	88.9 ± 2.3
PCL/S10	82.8 ± 1.2
PCL/S10/Z	81.0 ± 2.1
PCL/S20	78.4 ± 3.3
PCL/S20/Z	72.0 ± 1.1

Fig. 3. Weight gain after 24 hours immersion in saline solution at 37°C.

This increased hydrophilicity is expected to lead to better cell affinity to the zein added blend. Cell growth results indicated that this was the case (Fig. 4). After 1 day of cell culture, the number of cells on zein added blend was similar to that of PCL/starch blend. After 14 days, the advantage of adding zein to the blend was more apparent with the increase in cell number.

Fig. 4. Cell growth after 1 and 14 days.

4 Conclusions

Addition of zein to PCL/starch blends did not cause reinforcement effect. Zein did not perform well as coupling agent due to its partial immiscibility to PCL matrix and it did not compound with the starch. However, in terms of hydrophilicity, zein addition enhanced the blend's behavior.

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